

GA 21NRM02 - Digital-IT

D1 - Report on the realisation of a reference SAMU with up to 96 kSPS sampling rate and up to c. 40 kHz bandwidth

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METROLOGY PARTNERSHIP

Glossary

TERM	DEFINITION
1PPS	One Pulse Per Second – A signal used for precise time synchronization, often generated by GPS receivers.
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter – A device that converts analog signals into digital data for processing.
ASDU	Application Service Data Unit – A data structure used in communication protocols to encapsulate application-level data.
CALIBRATION	The process of adjusting and verifying the accuracy of a measurement instrument by comparing it to a known standard.
DCA	Direct Current Ammeter – An instrument used to measure direct current in an electrical circuit.
DMM	Digital Multimeter – An electronic measuring instrument that combines several measurement functions in one unit.
DUT	Device Under Test – The equipment or component being tested in a laboratory or field setup.
GRANDMASTER CLOCK	The primary source in a PTP network that distributes accurate time to all other devices.
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device – A microprocessor-based controller used in substations for protection, control, and monitoring.
LPIT	Low Power Instrument Transformer – A type of transformer that provides low power analog signals suitable for digital processing.
PHASE DISPLACEMENT	The angular difference between two waveforms, typically voltage and current, in an AC system.
POWER UTILITY PROFILE	A configuration of PTP designed specifically for power utility applications to ensure accurate time synchronization.
PTP	Precision Time Protocol – A protocol used to synchronize clocks throughout a computer network, defined in IEEE 1588.
RMS	Root Mean Square – A statistical measure of the magnitude of a varying quantity, commonly used in AC voltage and current measurements.
SAMU	Stand-Alone Merging Unit – Converts analog signals from conventional transformers into digital Sampled Values (SV) for IEC 61850 communication.
SAMPLE RATE	The number of samples taken per second from a continuous signal to convert it into a digital signal.
SAMPLED COUNT	The number of samples collected over a specific period or during a measurement process.
SAMPLED VALUE	A digital representation of an analog signal obtained by sampling at regular intervals.
SHUNTS	Low-resistance electrical components are used to measure current by producing a voltage drop proportional to the current flow.
TESTBED	A test setup or environment used for validating and verifying the performance of electrical devices or systems.
UNCERTAINTIES	The range of possible errors in a measurement, indicating the confidence level of the result.

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1 Summary

This document outlines the development of several reference devices used for the calibration of Stand-Alone Merging Units (SAMUs) that are used in the electricity grid. The ongoing transformation of the grid, driven by the integration of renewable energy sources, necessitates the use of SAMUs for further control and automation of the electricity grid. However, there are currently no services available to calibrate these merging units, and the lack of dedicated reference equipment hinders progress. Reliable calibration and testing starts with traceability (derived) from National Metrology Institute (NMI) level. Accredited test and calibration laboratories need verification of the accuracy of their equipment from an NMI. The focus is on the reference devices used in calibration facilities and their technical requirements for magnitude and timing accuracy evaluation. Other aspects like latency of gose messaging and synchronization problems are not part of this project. The document identifies key substation devices that can be calibrated using a reference SAMU, including other merging units, non-conventional instrument transformers, and test bridges.

2 Introduction

The ongoing transformation of the electric power sector, driven by the integration of renewable energy sources pushes the use of Stand Alone Merging Unit (SAMU) for the further control and automation of the electricity grid. Merging units are sold but there are no services to calibrate them. Also, the lack of dedicated reference equipment hinders progress. For the development of these services, a reference device is needed to calibrate against. This document describes the development of such a reference device.

Reliable testing starts with traceability from National Metrology Institute (NMI) level.

Accredited test and calibration laboratories need a verification of the accuracy of their test and calibration equipment from an NMI. First services involving IEC 61850-9-2 SV are now appearing at NMIs, but no comparisons between them have yet been reported. This is needed to provide verified calibration services for accredited test and calibration laboratories and instrument manufacturers.

Other important aspects for practical substation applications like latency of gose messaging, how such a device operates in a busy network or synchronisation problems are not part of the present project. The overviews provided in this document therefore concentrate on the reference devices that are used in the calibration facilities and their technical requirements for magnitude and timing accuracy evaluation.

To identify the relevant parameters for a performance evaluation of the accuracy of digital substation equipment, a few key substation components were identified and considered for investigation:

- Merging units (MUs) and stand-alone merging units (SAMUs)
- Non-conventional instrument transformers (ITs), including electronic ITs
- Test-equipment (Transformer bridges, IEC 61850 diagnostic equipment)

The relevant standards, if present, for these devices were consulted. The consulted standards should give a guideline on which parameters are key in the accuracy evaluation. If no standard is available for the device, like in the case of diagnostic equipment, the application of the device is considered and how it will be used.

From these applications the capabilities of the reference device can be derived.

Non-Conventional Transformers	Merging units	Digital test bridges

The testbed where the reference device can be used in has the general structure as depicted in fig. x.. More details on the testbed and the application of the reference SAMU can be found in the good practice guide D2.

3 Normative framework

Figure 1 shows the relative positions of different standards with respect to each other in the measurement part (IEC 61869) and on the other hand the data flow for metering (IEC 62052 & 62053), protection (IEC 60255), and switchgear (IEC 62271). This standards-review covers only the measurement standards. Focus is on parts “Electronic IT”, “SAMU”, and “Digital interface”. The definition for an electronic IT, according to IEC is a “LPIT in which signal processing is performed by active electronic components”. Additionally, the device will have a voltage or a digital output proportional to the primary current or voltage.

As regards to the output type, this review focuses only on digital output devices. The digital output is defined in IEC 61869-9, which includes the legacy output format defined in IEC 61850-9-2 LE. Stand-Alone Merging Units (SAMUs) are used for transforming analogue input signals and, rarely, proprietary digital outputs from ITs and LPITs into a standardized digital output. The SAMU standard IEC 61869-13 refers to IEC 61869-9 for data formatting and other aspects of the digital interface. The relation of each standard with respect to accuracy requirements is shown in Figure 2. The base standard IEC 61869-1 has been merged with the old 61869-6, which specified particular requirements for instrument transformers. The requirements are now given in part 1. IEC TC 38 are at this moment discussing the restart of work on IEC 61869 parts 7 and 8, and revision of parts 10 and 11

Figure 1: Position of different standards in the context of digital measuring and protection in an IEC 61850 substation environment

The SAMU standard IEC 61869-13 inherits performance requirements from the withdrawn IEC 61869-6, which are now given in IEC 61869-1. It also supplements the standard by introducing a higher accuracy class for a SAMU (measuring class 0,05) in support of the most accurate IT and LPIT measurement classes. Protection rated inputs for a SAMU are also introduced in part 13. The digital output, which is of interest in this review is defined in IEC 61869-9. It does not have any requirements for accuracy but does include some performance requirements for time synchronicity and digital output data latency. Measuring and protection rated device often have significantly different design goals and performance requirements. In case of being rated for protection applications, LPITs in IEC 61869-9 and SAMUs in IEC 61869-13 are required to also have a measuring class rating (clause 5.6 in IEC 61869-9/13). This is required due to protection class devices being often used also for measurement purposes.

Stand-alone merging unit

Figure 2: Relation of different IEC 61869 family standards with respect to accuracy requirements for LPITs and SAMUs

In Table 1 all the written standard that are referred to in this document are stated including their publication date.

Table 1. List of standards referred to in this document with their respective version.

Standard	Topic
IEC 61850-7-2:2020	Basic information and communication structure
IEC 61850-9-2:2011	Sampled values
IEC 61850-9-2 LE ???	Implementation guideline for IEC 61850-9-2
IEC 61850-9-3:2016	Power utility profile for PTP (IEEE 1588-2008)
IEC 61869	Instrument transformers
IEC 61869-1:2023	Instrument transformers - General requirements
IEC 61869-9:2016	Digital interface for instrument transformers
IEC 61869-13:2021	Stand-alone merging unit (SAMU)
IEC 62052	Electricity metering equipment
IEC 62053-22:2020	Static meters for AC active energy

4 Reference device global considerations

For testing SAMUs or other IEC 61850-9-2 SV equipment a testbed is needed. Within this testbed a device under test is being compared to a reference device. The testbed will be described in more detail in D2 [1].

Here we describe the consideration that must be considered in selecting or designing a reference device.

Figure 3: A general overview of a testbed showing the application of the reference device.

4.1 Signal measurement accuracy

The SAMU accuracy classes are shown in Table 2. The lowest four classes are also applicable to measuring LPITs with digital output in IEC 61869-9.

Table 2: SAMU accuracy classes taken from IEC 61869-13

Class	Ratio error [%]	Phase Displacement	
		[min]	[deg]
0,05	0.05	2.5	0.04
0,1	0.1	5	0.1
0,2	0.2	10	0.2
0,5	0.5	30	0.5
1	1	60	1.0

The strictest measurement class in IEC-61869 is the 0.05 % Class. The limits defined in an accuracy class are states as a ratio error and a phase displacement for a specific operating point. This operating point is defined as a frequency and a percentage of nominal voltage or current. The options stated in the norm for nominal voltages are: 100 V, 110 V, 115 V, 120 V, 200 V and 230 V, and these voltages divided by 3 or by the square root of 3. The possible nominal currents are: 1 A and 5 A. Considering the lowest and highest voltage and current options and the strictest class, this leads to the following specifications that must be met if all possible devices following this norm are to be calibrated: For the current magnitude the error must be less than 0.05% for currents between 20mA and 20A and less than 0.1% for lower currents down to 5 mA, at the nominal frequency.

The maximum voltage magnitude error is 0.05% for voltages between 6.7 V to 437 V and 0.1 % for lower voltages down to 667 mV at the nominal frequency.

The strictest phase error requirement is 2.5 minutes for nominal frequency, which corresponds to 1.9 us for 60 Hz. For harmonics the frequency is of course higher, but the requirements are less strict, making 1.9 us the strictest timing requirement. The ratio and phase errors are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Harmonic performance for the 0.05% class as defined in IEC-61869 (Table 1302)

Accuracy class (at f_R)	Ratio error at low frequency		Ratio error (\pm) at harmonics					Phase displacement (\pm) at low frequency	Phase error (\pm) at harmonics				
								Degrees	Degrees				
	0 Hz	1 Hz	2 nd to 4 th	5 th and 6 th	7 th to 9 th	10 th to 13 th	Above 13 th	1 Hz	2 nd to 4 th	5 th and 6 th	7 th to 9 th	10 th to 13 th	
0,05	+0,5 % -100 %	+0,5 % -30 %	0,5 %	1 %	2 %	4 %	+4 % -100 %	45	0,5	1	2	4	

NOTE 0 Hz in the first column means DC coupling is allowed but not required.

Measuring voltage and current simultaneously can introduce crosstalk errors. However, IEC-61869 mandates that crosstalk errors together with channel errors should not exceed the accuracy class limits.

The used sampling rates in SAMUs is defined in Table 4. Care should be taken that the reference device is capable of sampling at the same or higher rate as the device under test.

Table 4: List of sampling rates that are defined for different applications

Sample rate [Hz]	ASDUs per frame	Frame publishing rate [frames / s]	samples per nominal cycle		Remarks
			50 Hz	60 Hz	
4000	1	4000	80		protection application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 50 Hz systems
4800	1	4800		80	protection application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 60 Hz systems
4800	2	2400	96	80	Preferred rate for protection applications
5760	1	5760		96	60 Hz systems
12800	8	1600	256		measuring application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 50 Hz systems
14400	6	2400	288	240	Preferred rate for measuring applications
15360	8	1920		256	measuring application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 60 Hz systems
96000	1	96000			Preferred rate for high bandwidth DC application

4.2 Wiring systems: poly/single-phase setup

A MU usually has four inputs for voltage and four inputs for current. Three of the inputs are used to measure the voltage on L1, L2, and L3, while a fourth measures the neutral voltage. The same is true for the current channel. The neutral voltage and current are usually close to zero, only when there is an imbalance between the phases will there be neutral voltage and/or current. However, this channel does need to be calibrated. It can either be done by applying an unbalanced polyphase signal or measuring the fourth input separately.

There are two strategies when calibrating a MU.

- 1: calibrating each input separately, disconnecting or shorting the inputs that are not being measured

2: calibrating all inputs simultaneously using a poly phase grid.

Since it is unknown how the MU works internally, the calibration should happen in the same configuration as its intended use. Usually this would be a polyphase setup.

It is not recommended to put the current inputs in series as it might introduce errors due to common mode voltage on the current inputs. This is mainly visible in the phase displacement. When comparing a MU to the reference MU, the current inputs of the different MUs must be in series. The reference MU should be designed not to be affected by common mode voltage on the current input, so it can be connected to the high side of the current loop, ensuring the DUT MU has no common mode voltage on its current inputs.

Voltage inputs can be put in parallel, since IEC-61869 requires that crosstalk should be low enough to keep the device within specified accuracy limits. This means that any combination of channel input should not cause other channels errors to be outside the accuracy limits. However, the norm does not specify a way to test this requirement. The crosstalk requirement also allows for current and voltage to be calibrated simultaneously. There are no requirements on the phase between voltage and current (power factor), so it can be inferred that the crosstalk requirement holds for any power factor.

Grounding of the input channels needs to be considered carefully to ensure no common mode voltage on the current inputs while avoiding ground loops and leakage of measurement current to ground. The MU current input high should be floating, and the current low should be grounded at the current source. The same holds for the voltage input.

4.3 Time synchronization (1PPS or PTP)

Apart from voltage and current, PTP and 1 PPS timing signals need to be generated. The clock skew between these signals needs to be calibrated. And the influence of the switch, that distribute the signals, needs to be characterized.

Preferred time synchronization method in IEC 61869-9 is precision time protocol (PTP) defined in IEC 61588 (originally in IEEE 1588-2008). As a legacy option, ensuring compatibility of IEC 61850-9-2LE compliant equipment, 1PPS is allowed. Both standards prefer an optical fibre transmission of the 1PPS signal, but in practice also electrical 1PPS pulses can be found in measurement and test equipment. The latter is preferred for test purposes since physical time standards often have electrical output for their 1PPS reference signals. Conversion from and to an optical time reference will also introduce a delay with an associated uncertainty. The requirement for timing uncertainty delivered to measurement equipment through means of 1PPS is respectively $\pm 2 \mu\text{s}$ and $\pm 1 \mu\text{s}$ in IEC 61850-9-2LE and IEC 61869-9.

For PTP synchronization, the Power Utility Profile specified in IEC 61850-9-3 is required to be implemented in IEC 61869-9 compliant equipment. The profile includes among other things a limited subset of PTP functionalities, standardized message exchanges rates, and synchronization inaccuracy budgets for different networking equipment. For example, the peer-delay mechanism is explicitly required to be implemented. Message exchange rates are set as one per second, including the time-critical Sync and PDelay_Req messages. Support for both 1-step and 2-step clock mechanisms is mandatory. The lack of a physical and tangible timing reference means relating the phase of the signal encoded into an SV stream to an instance of time, which by definition is the start of a UTC-aligned second, and in practice a rising edge in a 1PPS signal becomes difficult

5 Reference devices

This document describes three different approaches that were taken in realizing a reference device that could be used in a SAMU testbed.

The system build by RISE uses an existing setup used for PMU calibrations. Modifying an existing setup to be able to serve as a reference is a cost-effective way and could help other NMIs adding this functionality to their setup. VSL uses a commercially available power meter to serve as a reference which would make the technique more accessible to (new) users. While VTT has taken the path of designing a custom digitizer to serve as a reference. Completely tailoring the needs of the device to the application.

The different implementations are described in the following sections.

5.1 Reference setup based on an existing PMU-calibration system

The reference setup is dependent on the frequency of the current and voltage signals used in the calibration of a device under test (DUT). Figure 4 shows a diagram of the setup for the frequency range 50 – 2000 Hz. This setup comprises a current and voltage generation system, and a reference measurement system for magnitude and phase displacement. Both the reference measurement system and the DUT, the SAMU in Figure 3, receive a 1PPS signal that originates from the official Swedish time scale UTC(SP). The magnitude and phase displacement readings of the DUT are calibrated by comparison with the reference system’s readings. The remaining of this section details the instrumentation that provides the reference measurement of voltage and current magnitude and phase displacement.

Figure 4: Setup for calibration of SAMU in the frequency range 40 – 2000 Hz.

5.1.1 Realisation of time and phase displacement reference, 50 Hz – 40 kHz

The time reference and the reference phase displacement measurement part of the system for the frequency range 50 Hz – 40 kHz are principally the same as given in Figure 4 for the frequency range 50 Hz – 2000 Hz.

For the realisation of these, two reference planes have been defined and their time delay relative UTC(SP) have been calibrated as portrayed in Figure 5:

- The time reference to the SAMU with expanded uncertainty, U_T
- The phase displacement reference with expanded uncertainty, U_ϕ

Figure 5: The position of the two calibrated reference planes for the realisation of time and phase displacement references

Realisation of time reference for the DUT

As portrayed in Figure 5, the time reference to the SAMU is using an optical 1PPS distribution which contributes with $k=1$ uncertainty of 30 ns. This pessimistic value is due to the non-accessible optical time reference plane. Improvement of this value requires well characterized and calibrated optical sensor.

The 1PPS fiber distributor consists of an Agilent branded HFBR-2412 TX module, which for the purpose of delay estimation as interfaced with a HFBR-2412 Rx module using three lengths of multi-mode fibre. It is assumed that the SAMU has a similar receiver with similar conditioning that yields similar characteristics. For the sake of clarity, the calibration of the time delay of the distribution establishes a reference plane at the optical connector of the SAMU.

The delay estimation attributes equal shares of delay to both the Tx and Rx modules.

Tx, Rx modules

F1, F2 – pair of MM fibers with ST connectors

F3 – single strand of MM fiber with SC connectors

C1- 1PPS source cable

The setup is expected to be sourced by the 1PPS distribution of the reference phase measurement system. In the delay estimation outputs 3 (Tx module) and 4 (CNT input A) were used. The counter used for calibration CNT91 was time base referenced by the WR frequency distribution from UTC(SP) not limiting the calibration results.

Estimates of the different components, measured differentially by the CNT-91 SN964665, 1 V trigger on both channels:

Component	Delay /ns	Std /ns	P2P /ns	N
PPS4-PPS3+ CNT+cbl	0.819	0.018	0.17	85360
C1+Tx+F1+F2+F3+Rx	164.207	0.437	3.69	61759
C1+Tx+F1+F2+F3+Rx	163.891	0.449	3.90	87060
C1+Tx+F1+F2+F3+Rx	163.798	0.431	2.57	373
C1+Tx+F1+Rx	126.653	0.426	3.28	8725
C1+Tx+F2+Rx	127.197	0.428	3.29	5902
C1+Tx+F1+F2+Rx	137.911	0.420	2.98	4697
C1+100ps adapter	6.091	0.019	0.17	13822
C1	5.9	0.05		
Tx, Rx	55.1	30	Equal distribution of delay	
F1	10.7	0.65		
F2	11.2	0.65		
F3	26.0	0.65		
C1+Tx+F1	71.7	30	For use with ST connector	
C1+Tx+F1+F3	97.7	30	For use with SC connector	

Uncertainties of the Tx/Rx are based on the assumption that both modules have substantial delays that may differ but are similar in value. Cable delays are based on the standard deviations of the measurements done. Delay estimates are rounded to 0.1 ns. Uncertainties are given as one-sigma values.

Figure 6

Figure 7

Realisation of phase displacement reference

The function and position of the phase displacement reference in the calibration system is presented in Figure 5 and consists of highly accurate voltage dividers and current shunts, an 8-channel, 16-bit analogue-to-digital converter (ADC), and a controller for the acquisition of the signals. The controller receives the reference 1PPS signal. PC1 communicates with the controller, receives the data, calculates the phase-angle of the current and voltage signals, and displays the results in degrees with respect to the 1PPS signal. The 1PPS link between UTC(SP) and the calibration system is common for both the Phase displacement reference and the SAMU under test, except for the electric-to-optical converter to the SAMU.

The uncertainty components for voltage and current phase displacement measurements, and the resulting combined ($k=1$) uncertainty U_T , are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Standard uncertainty contribution per uncertainty component for measurements of current and voltage phase displacement. Ranges are given in RMS values.

Uncertainty component	Current 12.5 mA – 1.2 A, Voltage 2 – 120 V, 50 Hz (deg)	Current 1 A, Voltage 100 V, 100 Hz – 40 kHz (ns)
Traceability reference instrument	5.76E-04	3.20E+01
Drift reference instrument	3.12E-04	1.73E+01
Resolution reference instrument	2.89E-07	1.60E+01
Short-time stability of the measured phase-angle of the generated signal		7.51E+01
Uncertainty due to frequency response of ADC (after correction)		5.77E+00
Combined uncertainty (k = 1)	0.0007	86

5.1.2 Voltage and current magnitude reference (50 – 2000 Hz)

The reference for voltage and current magnitude in the frequency range 50 – 2000 Hz is a ZERA COM 5003 power and energy reference meter, which has in turn been calibrated by comparison to RISE's references for RMS current and voltage. This instrument receives directly three voltage and three current signals in the magnitude range of interest of this project. The uncertainty components of a reference measurement of voltage and current magnitude are given in Table 6, as well as the combined ($k=1$) uncertainty.

It should be noted that an important part of the uncertainty stems from the fact that the phase and magnitude SAMU readings are evaluated from the fundamental frequency component and compared with the RMS value of the COM5003, including DC and harmonics.

Table 6: Standard uncertainty (% of reading) contribution of uncertainty components for reference measurement of current and voltage magnitude in the frequency range 50 – 2000 Hz. RMS values of current and voltage are given.

Uncertainty component	Current 12.5 mA, 50 Hz	Current 20 – 100 mA, 50 Hz	Current 0.2 – 1.2 A, 50 Hz	Voltage 2 – 120 V, 50 Hz	Current 1 A, 100 – 2000 Hz
Traceability reference instrument	7.50E-03	7.50E-03	7.50E-03	7.50E-03	1.73E-02
Drift reference instrument	2.31E-05	2.31E-05	2.31E-05	2.31E-05	8.66E-03

Resolution of reference reading	2.89E-05	2.89E-05	2.89E-05	2.89E-05	2.89E-07
Effect of the DC-value (from generation system) on the reference reading	1.66E-02	6.49E-03	6.50E-05	4.62E-04	2.60E-06
Effect of the high-frequency noise (from generation system) on the reference reading	2.89E-03	2.89E-03	2.89E-03	2.89E-03	2.89E-03
Combined uncertainty (k = 1)	0.019	0.011	0.008	0.008	0.020

5.1.3 Realisation of voltage and current magnitude reference (2 – 40 kHz)

The above reference for magnitude is not good for higher frequencies. The reference for voltage and current magnitude in the frequency range 2 – 40 kHz is therefore instead given by a voltage divider and a current shunt of own design with a bandwidth in the order of 10 MHz, and the ADC and controller from Figure 4. The ADC has a bandwidth of 520 kHz and a sampling frequency of 250 kS/s. Only one current and one voltage can be evaluated at a time with this setup.

The phase measurement parts are the same up to 40 kHz as at 2000 Hz, therefore the same uncertainty budget is applicable for the phase evaluation. For magnitude, the ADC has been calibrated by comparison to an instrument Fluke 5790A with traceability as shown in Table 7. The uncertainty components of a reference measurement of voltage and current magnitude using the ADC and the transducers are given in Table 7.

As mentioned above, it should be noted that an important part of the uncertainty stems from the fact that the phase and magnitude of the ADC readings are evaluated from a single frequency component which is calibrated by the comparison with the RMS value of the Fluke5790A, including DC and harmonics.

Table 7: Standard uncertainty (% of reading) contribution of uncertainty components for reference measurement of current and voltage magnitude in the frequency range 2 – 40 kHz. RMS values of current and voltage are given

Uncertainty component	Voltage 10 V, Current 0.1 A
Traceability Fluke 5790A	7.00E-03
Resolution reading ADC	7.22E-04
Uncertainty due to frequency response of ADC (after correction)	3.00E-02
Drift ADC	1.73E-03
Uncertainty due to non-linearity of ADC	7.75E-04
Uncertainty of transducer's scale factor	1.15E-03
Combined uncertainty (k = 1)	0.031

5.2 Commercial wattmeter as a reference SAMU

The use of a commercially of the shelf wattmeter makes this setup easily available to other laboratories to implement. Especially when using a wattmeter capable of synchronizing to IEC 1588. Although some dedicated software needs to be written to do a proper comparison. Some implementation details are given and a rough sketch on the software workflow that is used in this implementation of a reference SAMU.

5.2.1 Implementation

The setup, designed by VSL, for calibrating a SAMU is depicted in Figure 8. The heart of the setup is based on a Yokogawa WT5000 power analyser in combination with a PTP enabled switch (Cisco IE4000) and a Meinberg SyncBox.

The Syncbox is used to extract a copy of the 1 PPS synchronisation signal from the ethernet connection. The 1 PPS can be used to synchronise SAMUs with a 1 PPS input. Although in this application is it also used to increase the timing accuracy of the WT5000. In principle the switch doubles as a PTP master clock. But in the implementation shown here a PTP master clock is used, which gives the ability to calibrate the syncbox.

WT5000 can house up to seven power measurement modules. Each capable of measuring up to 1000 V, 30 A or 1000 V, 5 A at a sampling rate ranging from 10 kSps to 2 MSps. Usually, the 2 MSps sampling frequency is used. It can sync its time base to an IEC 1588 (PTP) source. Using the data streaming option the data from all channels is feed to the PC. No anti-aliasing filter is used giving the full bandwidth of 1 MHz, so the reference device can also be used to measure anti-aliasing filter attenuation of DUT.

Figure 8: VSL calibration setup

5.2.2 Magnitude calibration

The wattmeter with its modules can be calibrated by many commercial calibration services. The magnitude uncertainty requirements for the SAMU are relatively easy to achieve with a Wattmeter in this segment.

5.2.3 Inter module phase calibration

The skew between voltage channels is calibrated by putting channels in parallel while applying a signal on it (typically 50 Hz). This results in a inter module delay in the order of 10 ns.

5.2.4 Absolute delay calibration

The absolute delay calibration is a two-step process. First, the absolute delay of the combination of the PTP master, switch and Syncbox needs to be determined. Actually, the delay between the IEC 1588 (PTP) and the output of the Syncbox is of interest. Unfortunately, there is no direct access to the IEC 1588 embedded in the ethernet frames. This means that the total delay found in the calibration is an over estimation of the delay. Second, with a calibrated Syncbox the input delay of the wattmeter can be determined.

Syncbox calibration

During this calibration the total delay between the 1 PPS UTC on the input of the PTP master and the 1 PPS on the output of the Syncbox is determined. This is done using an oscilloscope. While calibrating, care must be taken in making the electrical paths are equal length. Also, the inputs of the oscilloscope needs to be interchanged to rule out any delay of the oscilloscope.

Calibrate the input delay of the WT5000

The 1 PPS coming from the syncbox is fed into the input of the WT5000. However, applying the 1 PPS directly to the voltage input doesn't give sufficient time resolution. The maximum sampling rate of the Wattmeter limits this to 500 ns. To improve the time resolution the vertical resolution of the digitizer is used. By passing the 1 PPS of the Syncbox through a slew rate limiter (first order lowpass) more points between the zero and the 1 state of the 1 PPS are made available. From these points we can fit a model of a first order lowpass filter through the data to determine the intersection with the "zero". This gives a resolution enhancement of about 5 times.

Figure 9: Slowed rising edge of the 1 PPS with a fit through the "Zero point" and a fit through the exponential rising of the points. The intersection is the sub-sample delay.

Figure 10: Sub-sample delay as a function of time.

The calibration results of the absolute delay of the wattmeter show a relatively large spread in the results. The specifications of the WT5000 are 10 μ s for PTP synchronization. In practice, this is better but the synchronization algorithm inside the WT5000 has difficulties making the synchronisation better than 2.5 μ s. However, the short-term stability of the internal time base is sufficient for the needs of calibrating a SAMU. For this reason, an additional input on the WT5000 is used during a SAMU calibration for time synchronisation. This gives a synchronisation with an uncertainty of better than 200 ns ($k=2$). While using PTP only would give 1 μ s ($k=2$).

Figure 11: Schematic overview of the 1 PPS calibration

5.2.5 Uncertainty

The uncertainty consists out of the calibration of the power meter and the delay calibration. The calibration of the power meter is done on the voltage and current ranges as described in the scope. This calibration can be performed by many commercial laboratories. The additional phase calibration with respect to the 1 PPS and/or the PTP1588 is described in chapter 3.2.4. The combined results are listed in Table 8.

Table 8: Total uncertainty for the VSL reference device

Uncertainty component	Magnitude	Phase
Reference device @ 50Hz Voltage and Current	0.011%	0.00225
Switch PTP delay		0.00036
Total (k=2)	0.022%	0.0052

5.2.6 Data workflow

Packets are recorded and filtered using Tshark while data is simultaneously collected from the WT5000. The process involves capturing network traffic through Tshark, while the WT5000 gathers precise measurement data. The data streams are subsequently aligned based on timestamp to ensure accurate comparison for each second, which helps maintain synchronization between both sources. Since only fractional seconds are available in the sampled value packets, care is taken to match corresponding data points from both sources as closely as possible, minimizing timing discrepancies. Both data recordings are initiated by a Python script, which automates the start of each collection session for consistency and repeatability. Finally, the results are displayed in a Jupyter notebook, allowing to visually compare and interpret the synchronized datasets using interactive graphs and tables.

5.2.7 Conclusion

The use of a commercially available wattmeter, such as the Yokogawa WT5000, in combination with a PTP-enabled switch and SyncBox, provides a practical and replicable setup for SAMU calibration. The system supports high sampling rates and PTP synchronization, enabling accurate magnitude and phase measurements. Calibration of inter-module skew and absolute delay demonstrates that the setup can meet the timing accuracy requirements for SAMU testing. The integration of data acquisition and network capturing, automated through Python and visualized in Jupyter, makes of a versatile workflow. While the WT5000's internal synchronization has its limitations, the use of an external 1 PPS input significantly improves timing accuracy, achieving uncertainties better than 200 ns (k=2), which is sufficient for the intended application.

5.3 Dedicated custom build reference SAMU

VTT's reference merging unit is a further development of a digitizer published in [2]. It supports up to 8 individually floating analog input channels and is built around a 16/32-bit integer arithmetic DSP processor board. The board has interfaces for serial buses to transfer data from the analog front-ends and to a PC via USB, and a 100Base-Tx ethernet connection for transmitting SV data. Firmware is updated to support sample data transmission in SV format specified in IEC 61850-9-2, including all predefined profiles from IEC 61869-9.

5.3.1 Physical design

The front ends are updated from [REF] with 20 or 24-bit successive approximation register (SAR) analog-to-digital converters (ADCs). The analog electronics preceding the ADC and the floating power supplies have been completely redesigned. The schematic is shown in XXX. The differential inputs are ESD protected and followed by unity gain buffers, which also drive an active guard of the input circuitry. A low-drift resistance network is used for setting the gain. Four-element devices implementing different resistance ratios can be used to set a desired gain value. Possible values are 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0, respectively yielding input ranges of ± 8 V, ± 4 V, and ± 2 V. Currently, the inputs are set for ± 8 V maximum input. The ADC is driven by a differential-output operational amplifier. A second-order multiple-feedback low pass filter can be implemented around the driver if desired. An R-C network at the ADC input is used for isolating the driver Op-Amp as charge storage to recharge the hold capacitor inside the ADC between consecutive sample instances. The R-C network forms a first-order low pass filter at 3.6 MHz. The design uses an oversized Zener diode followed by a low-drift resistance network and an Op-Amp buffer to generate a 5-V full-scale reference V_{ref} . The same reference source is used for biasing the ADC input to a common-mode voltage of 2.5 V. To facilitate easier calibration of the front-end delay, the PCB has an SMB connector labeled SCLK next to the ADC, which is used for measuring the sample clock signal timing. Additionally, the ADC input signals IN+ and IN- can be probed from easily accessible test points at the PCB.

Figure 12: Detailed schematic of VTT's reference SAMU front end.

Applicability of the reference device as an actual measurement standard calls for high level of stability and linearity. Gain of the device is calibrated at full-scale input using an AC standard resulting with uncertainty in the order of $10 \mu\text{V}/\text{V}$. While long term stability is not the highest priority, temperature drift of the gain has been one of the focus points in the front-end electrical design and has driven the choice of components in the front-end. Temperature coefficient of the gain is measured around the intended operating conditions of 23°C . Using a temperature step from 18°C to 28°C , the measured temperature coefficient of gain is below $1.3 \mu\text{V}/\text{V}/\text{K}$ for all 8 front ends.

A high degree of linearity helps with transferring traceability from a full-scale AC gain calibration to lower input magnitudes. Linearities of the inputs are measured using an 8-decade inductive voltage divider (IVD) using a 1-kHz signal. Linearity of the IVD is verified against another 8-decade IVD of different make. Figure 13 shows the linearity measurement result for an input magnitude from 100 % down to 5 % of full-scale. The gain variation stays within $17 \mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ for the entire tested range. Lower values require gain calibration at a specific input magnitude.

Figure 13: Gain linearity of VTT's reference SAMU front ends.

5.3.2 Absolute delay calibration method

For determining the absolute delay, we must include both the analog front-end delay and the internal delay (aperture delay) of the ADC. The absolute delay of the analog front-end is measured using an improved IEEE 1241 [3] method for ADC aperture delay measurement. The IEEE method suffers from input DC level influencing the results, while the method used by VTT negates the timing error caused by DC components in the signal chain. The method will also lend itself to a straightforward uncertainty evaluation of the measured delay.

The measurement setup is shown in Figure 14. A square wave signal with controlled slew rates, frequency f_{in} , and near-zero DC component is fed into the front-end (weighted solid line). The sample clock is set to frequency f_s , which is exactly two times higher than f_{in} and aligned such that the sample instances occur roughly at the rising and falling edges of the input signal. The input signal and the signal measured from the ADC sample clock pin SCLK are connected to an oscilloscope using equal length cables. The oscilloscope is connected to the same 10 MHz reference frequency as the signal generator and triggered at frequency f_s using its auxiliary trigger input and the trigger output from the signal generator. Additionally, the differential ADC input signal is measured using the oscilloscope, but the connection is removed when calibrating the delay to not influence the result.

Figure 14: Measurement setup for calibrating the absolute delay of the analog front ends

For determining the input delay, the phase of the sample clock is adjusted to receive no AC component in the data the reference device produces. This implies that the sample instants at the rising and falling edges occur when the signal has the same instantaneous value. Consequently, the input DC level is not important, which eliminates the error caused by improper handling of DC voltage. The oscilloscope is then used for recording the input voltage and the sample clock separately for rising and falling edges. Figure 15 shows example captures of the signals overlaid such that the sample clock edges for both recordings are time-aligned. The sample clock signal is set to cross the y-axis at around 2.6 V, which is the ADC's minimum input voltage

switching threshold for a logic ‘1’ as claimed by the manufacturer. An uncertainty component is introduced by the limited slew rate of the measured sample clock. First-order polynomials are fit to the input signal data near the crossing point using the least squares method and the crossing location is determined for the two resulting lines. The distance of the crossing point from the sample clock switching threshold is then determined, yielding the absolute delay of the front end. A similar measurement can be made for determining overall device delay, including sample clock propagation, by measuring at the clock input connector of the device instead of the SCLK pin of the ADC.

Figure 15: Overlaid rising and falling edges measured from card input connector. Sets of samples taken from the edges are drawn as round markers, whereas lines fit to the data are drawn as solid lines.

5.3.3 Uncertainty budgets

The reference device gain is calibrated using an AC calibrator with an uncertainty of 11.5 $\mu\text{V/V}$. Uncertainty of 8.5 $\mu\text{V/V}$ of AC gain linearity, shown in Table 9, is included based on the worst-case difference from average gain between 5 % and 100 % of full-scale. Lastly, an uncertainty component of 0.7 $\mu\text{V/V}$ is included to reflect the effect of the gain temperature coefficient in a laboratory environment, where the temperature is expected to remain within ± 0.5 degrees Celsius.

Reading measured signal timing from data illustrated in Figure 15 carries some uncertainty. We assume that the rising and falling slope crossing location can be determined with an uncertainty of ± 1 ns, which results in an uncertainty of 1.2 ns assuming a uniform distribution. For sample clock input timing we need to consider the input pin’s high-level threshold value. The measured signal around the threshold value, as seen in Fig 9, is changing rather slowly. We therefore carefully estimate the sample clock timing to be uniformly distributed between ± 3 ns of the measured value, which results in an uncertainty component of 3.5 ns. Cable delays are compensated for in the measurement, an estimated 1 ns uncertainty is used to account for uncertainty of the compensation.

During delay calibration procedure sample clock phase is adjusted with respect to input signal to receive no AC signal in sample data. However, the phase adjustment has finite resolution, which results in a timing uncertainty component. If we denote the timing resolution of the signal generator with t_{SG} , the error will be uniformly distributed within the range $[-0.5t_{SG}, 0.5t_{SG}]$. A sample rate of 16384 Hz and phase resolution of 0.01° results in an uncertainty component of 1.0 ns.

Table 9: Total gain uncertainty for VTT’s reference SAMU

Uncertainty component	Value
Calibration (50 Hz)	11.5
Linearity (5 % ... 100 %)	8.5
Temperature coefficient ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$)	0.7
Total ($k = 2$)	28.6

Table 10: Total timing uncertainty for VTT's reference SAMU

Uncertainty component	Value
Sample clock location	3.5
Input crossing location	1.2
Sample clock phase resolution	1.0
Cables, delay calibration	1.0
Total [ns] ($k = 2$)	8.0
Total [mdeg] ($k = 2$)	0.14
Total [min] ($k = 2$)	0.009

5.3.4 Simulated SV data generator

Besides generating SV data based on measured signals at its inputs, VTT's reference device can simulate current and voltage signals and produce a completely artificial SV stream. This functionality may be used in the future for calibrating digital energy and power quality meters and phasor measurement units. The SV data simulator is built using the direct digital synthesis (DDS) approach for signal generation. A DDS generator relies on a look-up table, where the instantaneous values of a single cycle of sinusoid is stored. The phase information of a desired output signal is stored and constantly updated in a phase accumulator. Its value is used for retrieving entries from the look-up table to construct a sinusoid at a desired frequency. The output frequency f_{out} is given by the basic DDS equation in the general case by

$$f_{out} = \frac{M \times f_s}{k \times 2^n},$$

where M is the phase accumulator increment, f_s is the reference or update frequency, k is the accumulator oversampling factor if one is used, and 2^n is the number of entries in the look-up table. The value of M needs to be truncated to a reasonable length to limit the size of the look-up table. This often results in unwanted but usually small error in output frequency as well as spurious frequency tones in the output spectrum. In the specific case of generating SV streams using DDS, it is possible to overcome the adverse effects of phase accumulator truncation and limited look-up table size by enforcing minimum resolution in output frequency and starting phase. This, together with a properly chosen size for the look-up table and phase accumulator decimation factor will produce an SV stream with practically no uncertainty in any of its properties, including frequency. Solving the above equation for M , the phase accumulator step for a desired output frequency is given by

$$M = \frac{k \times 2^n \times f_{out}}{f_s},$$

The look-up table size 2^n is chosen based on the standard sample rates in IEC 61869-9. A lowest common denominator for all the sample rates is 1152000. Selecting $2^n = 115200$ as the size for the look-up table results in integer division for any integer output frequency f_{out} . This yields a value of roughly 20.1 for n in the DDS equation, indicating that if a 32-bit phase accumulator is used, an oversampling factor of $k = 1000$ ($\approx 2^{10}$, or around 10 bits) is possible. A single bit is spared for checking accumulator overflow. The oversampling factor of 1000 increases the no-error output frequency to 1 mHz. If the output frequency f_{out} is given in millihertz, the phase accumulator step equation can be rewritten as

$$M = \frac{k \times 1152000}{f_s} \times \frac{f_{out}[mHz]}{1000},$$

which yields only integer values for M given the available sample rates f_s . The minimum available frequency resolution for each sample rate can be calculated using

$$\Delta f_{out,min} = \frac{f_s}{k \times 2^n} = \frac{f_s}{k \times 1152000}.$$

The minimum frequency resolution for all IEC 61869-9 sample rates is given in Table 11.

Table 11: Minimum frequency resolution of SV data for each sample rate

IEC 61869-9 sample rate f_s [Hz]	Minimum frequency resolution $\Delta f_{out,min}$ [μ Hz]
4000	3.5
3800	4.2
12800	11.1
14400	12.5
15360	13.3

For calibrating active power energy meters, the power factor embedded in the SV streams becomes important. The phase difference between the current and voltage signals in the SV stream should therefore be well defined. Phase accumulator starting value M_0 corresponding to a starting phase φ_0 can be written as

$$M_0 = \frac{\varphi_0 \times 2^n}{360^\circ} = \frac{\varphi_0 \times 1152000}{360^\circ}$$

If the starting phase is given in multiples of 5 millidegrees, no rounding errors for M_0 will be received. The above equation then simplifies to

$$M_0 = \frac{16 \times \varphi_0 [m^\circ]}{5 [m^\circ]}$$

The 5 millidegree no-error phase resolution is fine enough to set the power factor with a resolution below 0.001. As an example, a phase difference of 30° translates to a power factor of 0.86602, which can then be used for calculating the active power in the SV stream for the meter. The minimum available phase resolution for $M = 1$ is around $0.31 m^\circ$. Even without calculating the actual power factor due to limited phase resolution, the actual power factor error remains small. This is shown in Figure 16, where any arbitrarily chosen power factor results in an active power error less than 0.005% per apparent power.

Figure 16

The generator is implemented on a 600-MHz integer arithmetic DSP inside VTT's reference merging unit. The look-up table residing in off-chip 133 MHz SDRAM has a 32-bit vertical resolution in order not to limit the inherent 32-bit resolution in the SV stream samples. Two accesses to SDRAM are required for fetching a value, since the data bus is only 16 bits wide. Regardless of the limited hardware, the generator performs

extremely fast due to low calculation requirements to produce a single instantaneous sinusoid value. Calculating a single harmonic component takes roughly 365 ns resulting in a maximum of 2.74 million instantaneous values per second, enough to produce several harmonic components for all current and voltage signals even for highest sample rates. During the calculation, data is fetched from the look-up table, scaled to match the desired instantaneous magnitude for the sinusoid and added to the SV sample after which the phase accumulator is increased and wrapped in case of overflow. Finally, a DC level is added to the sample before it's transmitted as SV data.

6 Sampled Values analysis.

For the determination of the difference between the reference and the device under test special software is needed. The data coming from the merging unit are individual samples this needs to be converted to terms like magnitude error and phase error.

6.1 Software requirements

The stream of Sampled Values stream must be received and processed to check the validity of the data and extract the parameters that give the measurement value. Concerning to the acquisition step, a standard tool such as tcpdump, tshark or Wireshark can be used. Next, the data can be processed to extract the samples from the acquisition format (pcap in the case of the previous examples) and check the validity of the stream. Validation can include checks for missing samples, reported synchronization status and reported quality. Finally, if the data pass all control checks, the parameter of magnitude or phase can be extracted from the Sampled Values stream. These steps are covered in the next subsections.

6.2 Magnitude units

The IEC 61869-9 enforces the use of 0.001 A and 0.01 V as values for the Least Significant Bytes. The software should use these units to interpret the raw data coming in the SV stream. Additionally, to recover the input signal, the software must consider also the voltage and current transformer ratios configured in the SAMU.

6.3 Parameter extraction from waveform

The software should recover at least amplitude and absolute phase from the values coming in the SV stream. These parameters should be compared with the reference to obtain magnitude and phase displacement error for all the points listed in the standard. Additional to amplitude and phase, it is recommended to report the reconstructed frequency and offset of the output waveform. These parameters help to detect possible errors in the input settings or the signal chain. Recommended algorithms for parameter extraction are 4-parameter sine fitting and 3-point Hann window FFT fitting. [4,5]

7 Conclusions

It is noted that non-time-critical parameters like rms magnitude, linearity, relative phase, and harmonic response are not unique to the digital substation equipment and accredited services for these parameters are already in principle available. The main provision is that the calibration and test providers should add interfacing to the IEC 61850-9-2 interface to their existing calibration and test setups to read out the readings of the digital instrumentation.

The key parameter which is difficult to determine for all digital instrumentation is the absolute phase of the SV stream with respect to the 1 PPS or IEC 1588 timing reference. This feature is unique to equipment equipped with sample value stream outputs/inputs and this is where the main challenge lies when it comes to accredited, traceable evaluation of this kind of digital instrumentation. Optional further investigations can be done on some more unique features of digital substation equipment like the latency of a SAMU or IT which includes the processing time and the frequency response of the input as well as protection-related parameters i.e., composite error.

The performance of the presented implementations of the reference SAMU are demonstrated in D2 [1] and by means of an intercomparison. In this intercomparison a SAMU was sent around to the different laboratories for calibration. The results of this comparison are published in [6].

8 References

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